

Critical Medicines Act: analysis of the challenges and the path to health and pharmaceutical sustainability

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Abstract

This study represents a desk-based research analysis aimed at examining the European Commission's draft regulation—the Critical Medicines Act (CMA)—designed to strengthen the availability and security of supply of critical medicinal products within the European Union (EU). Through a systematic review of legislative documents, strategic reports, official statements, and scientific publications, the study identifies the main objectives, instruments, and potential weaknesses of the proposed framework. The analysis emphasizes the need to balance European strategic autonomy with the national sovereignty of Member States in the field of healthcare. The results indicate that, despite the CMA's significant potential to enhance pharmaceutical security, challenges related to administrative burden, EU-level coordination, and the feasibility of implementation timelines remain substantial. The study concludes with recommendations for optimizing implementation and reducing bureaucratic and logistical barriers.

Keywords

active pharmaceutical ingredients, critical medicinal products, European Union, pharmaceutical policy, strategic autonomy, supply security

Introduction

In the context of escalating challenges related to health crises, geopolitical tensions, and the global dependence on imports

of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) from third countries, this article systematizes the main objectives, instruments, and potential weaknesses, including implementation challenges, of the European Commission's proposed

Regulation establishing a framework to strengthen the availability and security of supply of critical medicinal products and medicines of major public interest. Special emphasis is placed on the balance between the European Union's strategic autonomy and the preservation of the Member States' national competences in the field of healthcare. The analysis highlights that the success of this initiative depends on proportionality, coherence with other legislative processes, and effective engagement of all relevant stakeholders.

The so-called Critical Medicines Act (CMA) represents an ambitious policy instrument aimed at reinforcing the pharmaceutical resilience and strategic autonomy of the European Union. However, its effectiveness will largely depend on the ability of Member States and the European Commission to ensure coordinated implementation and to avoid administrative overlaps. Particular attention should be paid to the realism of the proposed timelines and the integration of the CMA with the broader Pharmaceutical Package.

Overview of the Critical Medicines Act

The proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a framework to strengthen the availability and security of supply of critical medicinal products, as well as of medicinal products of major public interest, is structured into eight chapters (European Commission 2025b). The legal basis for the proposed Regulation is Article 114 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), which enables the harmonization of legisla-

tion related to the functioning of the internal market. In accordance with paragraph 3 of the same article, the proposal also aims to ensure a high level of human health protection (Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union 2007).

Accordingly, the proposal addresses a comprehensive set of instruments designed to respond to systemic weaknesses in medicine supply chains that have been identified in the context of health emergencies, geopolitical disruptions, or market constraints (European Commission 2025a). The figure below illustrates the general principles and objectives that the proposed Regulation seeks to achieve (Fig. 1).

Its main objectives are:

- to complement existing legislation with a focus on the sustainable supply of critical and essential medicines;
- to strengthen coordination between the Member States and the European Commission;
- to encourage investment in strategic projects aimed at reinforcing production and reducing vulnerabilities within supply chains;
- to introduce new criteria for public procurement that account for reliability and EU manufacturing capacity, not solely price;
- to establish a Coordination Group for Critical Medicines to support the joint implementation of the Regulation;
- to foster international cooperation with third countries in the areas of raw materials and manufacturing;
- to ensure consistency with other EU legislative instruments and provide for a regular evaluation of the Regulation's effectiveness every 5 years.

CRITICAL MEDICINES ACT OVERVIEW

Figure 1. Overview of the draft regulation on critical medicines.

Methodology

The study is based on a desk analysis (review of secondary data) of published legislative documents, technical reports, and scientific publications. The sources include European institutions (European Commission, EMA, DG HERA) and official EU legal acts, as well as a review of academic papers indexed in databases such as Scopus and PubMed. The analysis employs an interdisciplinary approach—legal, political, and pharmaceutical—identifying key aspects of the proposed legislation and its potential impact on Member States.

Data collection method

Data were collected through a systematic documentary analysis of official publications, legislative proposals, and reports from the European Commission, DG HERA, and the European Medicines Agency (EMA). A purposive sampling method was applied to select documents relevant to the topics of pharmaceutical security and supply chain resilience. The data were structured into five analytical categories: (1) regulatory framework, (2) CMA instruments, (3) administrative and environmental challenges, (4) national sovereignty and strategic autonomy, and (5) strategic stockpiles and logistics.

Data collection period

The data were gathered between March 2024 and July 2025, covering documents published between 2020 and 2025, with a focus on European Commission legislative initiatives developed after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Number of data sources

A total of more than 35 sources were analyzed, including legislative proposals, technical reports, academic publications, and strategic policy documents. Of these, 12 were primary EU legal and institutional sources, while the remainder consisted of academic and analytical works.

Preprocessing of data

Prior to analysis, the data were organized in a table according to source type (legislative, institutional, academic) and grouped by thematic category: regulatory framework, CMA mechanisms, administrative burden, environmental requirements, national sovereignty, and strategic stockpiles. Duplicate documents and outdated versions were excluded from the final dataset.

Specific features of data collection

Only official and verified publications were used, accessed through the websites of EU institutions and international academic databases. Due to the evolving nature of the

legislative process, some of the analyzed documents were in draft form—a factor that was duly acknowledged as a limitation of the study.

Results

1. Regulatory framework

The Critical Medicines Act aims to establish a unified European framework for managing the risk of shortages of critical medicines through EU-wide mechanisms for supply chain monitoring and control. Its main legal basis is Article 114 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), seeking to balance the functioning of the internal market with the protection of public health. The CMA consists of eight chapters covering objectives, instruments, coordination, investment, public procurement, and international cooperation.

2. Mechanisms and instruments

The proposal provides for the establishment of a Coordination Group for Critical Medicines, the introduction of accelerated authorization procedures, and the designation of strategic projects to strengthen pharmaceutical production within the EU. Mandatory criteria for public procurement (MEAT) are introduced, and Member States are required to develop national sustainable supply programs within 6 months of the Regulation's entry into force.

3. Administrative and environmental challenges

Implementing the CMA will require significant expert and administrative capacity. There is a risk of overlapping functions and an increase in administrative burden, particularly for Member States with limited resources. Greater clarity is needed regarding the interaction between the CMA and existing environmental legislation, such as Regulation (EU) 2024/1252 on Critical Raw Materials—to avoid inconsistencies and procedural delays.

4. National sovereignty and strategic autonomy

The analysis highlights a potential conflict between the EU's pursuit of collective strategic autonomy and the preservation of national competences. According to Article 168(7) of the TFEU, Member States retain responsibility for the organization of their healthcare systems. Therefore, the CMA should be implemented in a proportional manner that respects this principle.

5. Strategic reserves and logistics

The CMA encourages the establishment of an EU-level strategic reserve of medicines; however, the requirement

to share data on national stockpiles raises concerns related to confidentiality and national security. Participation of Member States in such initiatives should therefore remain voluntary and proportionate.

Discussion

The analysis demonstrates that the Critical Medicines Act is an ambitious instrument aimed at strengthening pharmaceutical resilience across the European Union. However, its effectiveness will depend on the degree of coordination with other legislative initiatives, such as the Pharmaceutical Package. Success will also hinge on the ability to adapt implementation measures to the specific administrative capacities and market conditions of individual Member States.

Challenges in the negotiation process

The drafting and negotiation of the Critical Medicines Act (CMA) take place within the broader framework of the ongoing revision of EU pharmaceutical legislation and the new EU Strategy on Medical Countermeasures (European Commission 2025c, 2023). A central issue concerns the role of Member States in defining their own health priorities. According to Article 168(7) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), the organization and delivery of healthcare services remain a national competence, which necessitates a careful balance between the Union's strategic autonomy and Member States' sovereignty (Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union 2007).

Timeframes and coordination

Following the COVID-19 crisis, the need to strengthen the supply chains for critical medicines—especially those used in hospital care—became evident (Stoev and Lebanova 2025). Nevertheless, the proposed CMA introduces ambitious and, in some cases, unrealistic implementation deadlines. Article 19 requires Member States to establish national programs to safeguard medicine supply chains within 6 months of the Regulation's entry into force, a timeline that may prove difficult for many administrations (Bartlett 2024). Additionally, cross-references to other legislative proposals still under negotiation, such as the Pharmaceutical Package, risk creating legal overlaps and uncertainty (Hoppe 2020).

Administrative burden and expert capacity

The proposal's provisions on new administrative structures and expert responsibilities lack sufficient clarity. Without clear delineation of competences and resource allocation, Member States may face significant administrative pressure, particularly those with limited institutional capacity (Fernández-I-Marín et al. 2024). Avoiding duplication of functions and tasks is essential, as excessive bureaucratic complexity can undermine motivation and efficiency. The

European Commission should therefore ensure adequate expert support at the EU level rather than relying excessively on national administrations.

Accelerated procedures and environmental requirements

While accelerated procedures for strategic projects could reduce bureaucratic obstacles and stimulate investment, they also pose risks to regulatory quality. Shortened timelines for GMP inspections and environmental assessments may compromise oversight and compliance (Stephan Rönninger et al. 2021; Abdullayev et al. 2024). The environmental provisions in Articles 11 and 12 should be harmonized with Regulation (EU) 2024/1252 on Critical Raw Materials to ensure legal consistency and procedural coherence (European Parliament 2024).

Public procurement and coordination mechanisms

The mandate and functions of the Coordination Group for Critical Medicines must be clearly defined to ensure effective implementation without encroaching on national competences. The introduction of a mandatory Most Economically Advantageous Tender (MEAT) criterion in procurement may limit Member States' flexibility, particularly those with lower GDP (García-Altés et al. 2023). Price should remain the primary criterion, while other factors may be applied voluntarily according to national contexts. Empirical evidence indicates that direct investments in research and development are more effective in enhancing the competitiveness of the European pharmaceutical sector than indirect fiscal incentives (Yang and Xu 2023).

National stockpiles and confidentiality

The establishment of EU-level strategic reserves is an important step toward enhanced preparedness, but it raises logistical and confidentiality concerns. Data on national medicine stockpiles are often classified as state secrets, and their disclosure must follow a voluntary and proportionate approach (Grigorov et al. 2023a, 2023b; Azai and Laryea 2025). Achieving a balance between strengthening supply security and maintaining the principle of free movement of goods within the internal market is essential (Grumiller et al. 2021).

The path toward pharmaceutical resilience

Despite these challenges, the Critical Medicines Act represents a strategic milestone in the transformation of European pharmaceutical policy. Its direct focus on addressing medicine shortages and reducing dependence on third countries is crucial for long-term sustainability and autonomy (Spieske et al. 2022). Through initiatives such as the Union List of Critical Medicines and the Alliance for Critical Medicines, the CMA seeks not only to regulate but

also to foster innovation, diversification, and production within the EU. The choice of a regulation—rather than a directive—ensures immediate and uniform application across all Member States, positioning the CMA as a cornerstone of the broader Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe.

Limitations of the study and perspectives

This study is based entirely on secondary sources, which implies certain limitations regarding the timeliness and completeness of the available information. Some of the analyzed documents are still in draft form, which may result in changes before the final adoption of the Critical Medicines Act. The lack of access to internal working documents of EU institutions also constitutes a limitation. Future research could focus on an empirical assessment of the Regulation's impact on national healthcare systems, including interviews with key stakeholders and quantitative evaluations of its effect on medicine supply and accessibility.

Conclusion

Despite the ambitious objectives and potential benefits of the Critical Medicines Act (CMA)—which include enhancing the preparedness and resilience of healthcare systems, promoting domestic production, and establishing a long-term regulatory framework—its implementation faces several challenges. These include concerns related to national sovereignty, administrative burden on Member States, the need for realistic implementation timelines, and potential issues regarding joint procurement procedures and the management of strategic reserves.

The success of the Critical Medicines Act will depend on the European Union's ability to balance these diverse interests and address existing concerns effectively. If these challenges are managed successfully, the CMA has the potential to ensure a more secure and sustainable pharmaceutical supply chain across Europe. This would not only guarantee continuous access to essential medicines for EU citizens but also strengthen the Union's strategic position on the global stage, transforming dependency into autonomy and vulnerability into resilience. Ultimately, by overcoming emerging challenges, the Act could transform the EU's reliance on external sources into strategic independence, thereby safeguarding the health security of millions of Europeans and reinforcing the Union's role as a global leader in the pharmaceutical industry.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

A.T.: conceptualization of the study, patient management, manuscript drafting, and critical revisions; D.M.: literature review, data collection, and interpretation of clinical findings; V.M.: preparation of figures and discussion section; E.P.G. and G.B.: diagnostic data analysis, cardiological evaluation, and clinical correlation; A.M. and N.P.: pharmacological review and contribution to manuscript editing; S.G.: supervision, final approval of the manuscript, and overall coordination of the study. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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